

Suspicious Bank Card Transaction Recognition Based on K-means Clustering and Random Forest Algorithm

Yunxiang Liu, Zeshen Tang, Wenjie Zheng
School of Computer Science and Information Engineering
Shanghai Institute of Technology
Shanghai, China
yxliu@sit.edu.cn, tangzs808@foxmail.com

Abstract: Suspicious transactions are hidden in thousands of massive transaction data, causing incalculable losses and risks, but the detection is very difficult. In terms of how to effectively explore and identify suspicious transactions from massive transaction data accurately and quickly, this paper adopts the method based on the combination of k-means algorithm and random forest algorithm to solve the problem of data imbalance in the identification of suspicious transactions in bank accounts, and proposes an effective suspicious transaction detection model. At the same time, the AUC(Area Under Curve) and Recall indicators such as the unbalanced data classification standard of performance evaluation, and finally to Kaggle data platform for the bank account of suspicious transactions data set, the results show that the proposed detection model of performance evaluation index AUC increased by 5%, F1-measure increases by 1%, show that the method has some reference value to the suspicious transactions recognition, limited information utilization rate is higher, which makes all kinds of Banks prediction speed and accuracy of suspicious transactions events get improved, can to some extent, reduce the operating cost and risk of the banking sector.

Keywords: Big data, K-means Algorithm, Random Forest, Suspicious Identification, Unbalanced Data

I. INTRODUCTION

Suspicious transactions in bank accounts not only, bring great risks to the banking industry, but also seriously affect the interests of merchants and bank customers, causing significant direct or indirect losses of varying degrees. The design of efficient fraud detection algorithms is key for reducing these losses, and more and more algorithms rely on advanced machine learning techniques to assist fraud investigators. The design of fraud detection algorithms is however particularly challenging due to non-stationary distribution of the data, highly imbalanced classes distribution and continuous streams of transactions [1]. Traditional methods to judge suspicious patterns are mostly based on the basic theory of statistics, and some constructed models are used for analysis. And some assumptions are taken as the premise, such as stationarity hypothesis, the normal distribution hypothesis, etc. [2]. In practical

applications, the rate of missed detection and false alarm rate is too high.

Frauds occur rarely compared to the total amount of transactions. Learning from unbalanced datasets is a difficult task since most learning systems are not designed to cope with a large difference between the numbers of cases belonging to each class. Traditional methods for classification with unbalanced datasets rely on sampling techniques to balance the dataset. However, it is also a question how to effectively sample representative and differentiated samples from such a large data set.

In the area of suspicious bank account transaction identification, we can distinguish between methods that operates at the data algorithmic levels. At the data level, balancing techniques are used as a pre-processing step to rebalance the dataset or to remove the noise between the two levels, the classification algorithms themselves are adapted to deal with the minority class detection. In

Corresponding Author: Zeshen Tang. School of Computer Science and Information Engineering, Shanghai Institute of Technology, China. E-mail: tangzs808@foxmail.com

this article we focus on data level techniques as they have the advantage of leaving the algorithms unchanged.

In the process of clustering, k-means clustering algorithm needs to gradually adjust the weight of features, that is, continuously increase or decrease the weight of features according to the results of each iteration, so as to finally establish the contribution degree of each feature in the clustering after the completion of clustering [3]. In this paper, a feature weighted k-means clustering algorithm based on Fisher's linear discrimination rate is adopted. Fisher's judgment basis [4] is a feature selection method based on distance. Its main idea is to identify features with better classification effect. In other words, the smaller the distance between classes, the larger the distance between classes. Using this property, after each iteration clustering, the contribution degree of each feature after the iteration clustering is obtained according to this criterion, and the weight of the feature is calculated according to this contribution degree. Since the feature contribution degree after the iterative clustering can be obtained according to Fisher linear criterion, the calculated feature weight does not need to be adjusted step by step according to the previous feature weight, which improves the clustering effect. The whole process no longer requires additional parameters, significantly saves the time of test parameters, and improves the stability of the algorithm. Random forest is actually a special bagging method that uses decision trees as the model [5]. First, m a training set is generated by the bootstrap method, then, for each training set, constructing a decision tree, in the node to find characteristics were falling apart, cannot find the characteristic of all indicators (such as information gain) of the largest, but in the random part of characteristics, in the middle of the smoke to the characteristics of the find the optimum solution, is applied to the node, to split. Due to bagging, which is the idea of integration, the method of random forest is actually equivalent to sampling both samples and features (if the training data is regarded as a matrix, as is common in practice, it is a process in which both rows and columns are sampled), so overfitting can be avoided.

The best technique for unbalanced data may depend on several factors such as i) data distribution ii) classifier used iii) performance measure adopted, etc. The suspicious transaction ration is too small compared with the total transaction amount, which is a highly

unbalanced dataset. Therefore, common performance measurement standards adopted by the classifier, such as the accuracy, are not suitable for the unbalanced problem. Using AUC value can ensure that you can accurately measure the performance of the model when the sample is unbalanced.

II. DESCRIPTION OF EXPERIMENTAL ALGORITHM

A. K-means Feature Weighted Clustering Based on Fisher Criterion

A large number of high-dimensional data packets contain many redundant features and even noise features. Therefore, the reasonable selection of features in high-dimensional data can effectively remove irrelevant and redundant features, so as to improve the efficiency of the learning algorithm and reduce the computational complexity [6].

Fisher criterion is one of the effective methods for feature selection. By using the Fisher ratio of each feature as the basis for the classification and ordering of features, features with better discrimination effect can be found, so as to achieve the purpose of reducing the dimensions and achieving better recognition performance.

In the process of feature selection, training samples are set $\{(x_1, y_1), (x_2, y_2), \dots, (x_n, y_n)\}$,

Where n is the sample number, $x_i \in R^k$, K is the dimension of the eigenvector, $y_i = \{-1, 1\}^l$ label for a category, 1 for the positive class, -1 for the negative class. Each class contains n_i samples, $x_i^{(k)}$, $m_i^{(k)}$, and $m^{(k)}$ are respectively the values of sample x_i of category i , average of sample i , and mean of all samples in dimension k . $S_B^{(k)}$ and $S_\omega^{(k)}$ are used to represent the inter-class variance and intra-class variance of this dimension on the training sample set[7].

$$S_B^{(k)} = \sum_{i=1}^2 \frac{n_i}{n} (m_i^{(k)} - m^{(k)})^2 \quad (1)$$

$$S_\omega^{(k)} = \frac{1}{n} \sum_{i=1}^2 \sum_{x \in \omega_i} (x^{(k)} - m_i^{(k)})^2 = \frac{1}{n} (\delta_1^2 + \delta_2^2) \quad (2)$$

Then, the Fisher criterion ratio of a single feature can be expressed as

$$J_{fisher}(k) = S_B^{(k)} / S_\omega^{(k)} \quad (3)$$

From equation (3), it can be known that the Fisher ratio of features is J_{fisher} . The larger the Fisher ratio of a certain dimension feature on the training set is, the better the classification ability of the dimension feature is, and the more recognition information is included, the value of noise feature J_{fisher} is close to zero.

Applying Fisher's linear discriminant rate criterion above, the weighted k-means data clustering algorithm is obtained as follows:

1. Assign the same weight to the used features, and apply the k-means algorithm for initial clustering.
2. For the clustering results, Fisher linear discrimination rate was used to calculate the contribution degree 1 of each feature component in the clustering, and the weight of each feature was calculated according to the contribution degree:

$$w_d = \frac{J_{fisher}(d)}{\sum_{k=1}^d J_{fisher}(d)}; d = 1, 2, \dots, D \quad (4)$$

Then, weighted K clustering centers obtained in the clustering were recalculated, and the weighted distance from each data object to each clustering center was calculated by using equation (5).

$$diss(x_m, c_k) = \sum_{d=1}^D w_d \times d(x_{md}, c_{kd}) \quad (5)$$

3. According to the shortest weighted distance from each data object to each clustering center, the members of the data object are classified and assigned again, and skip to step 2 to calculate the contribution degree of each feature after clustering again, and update the clustering center until the clustering center is basically stable, that is, the clustering is completed when equation (6) is satisfied.

$$|SSE^{(l+)} - SSE^{(l)}| \leq \varepsilon \quad (6)$$

Where: experience setting $\varepsilon = 0.03$. The pseudo-code of the whole clustering process is shown as following:

Input: M data object sets (each data object has D-dimensional characteristics), K clustering number.

Output: M clustering index corresponding to data objects, K clustering centers.

The begin

K clustering centers were randomly selected.

Set the weight of each feature as $1/D$.

Repeat

According to equation (5), each data object is assigned to the nearest cluster to K clustering centers, and K clusters are preliminarily formed.

Renew the center of each cluster;

By formula (3), the Fisher discrimination rate of each one-dimensional feature was calculated.

Through equation (4), calculate and update feature weight F;

Until the clustering center is basically stable, that is, equation (6) is satisfied.

The end

B. Combination of K-means Clustering and Radom Forest Algorithm

In many cases, the simple decision tree may cause over-fitting due to the training data set. In order to prevent this situation, pruning is needed, but excessive pruning will lead to poor classification effect of the decision tree model. In addition, the greedy algorithm is mostly used in the establishment of decision trees, which may cause the prediction results of the model to be partial and fail to get the best results.

Random forest is a combination classifier with multiple decision trees formed based on CART algorithm [8]. It composes of the basic meta-classifier CART decision tree. CART decision tree is an algorithm with insufficient stability, so bootstrap is needed to re-sample to create multiple random vectors, and then each random vector is turned into a completely pruneless decision tree, and multiple decision trees are used to construct the combination model [9]. This can improve the overall generalization performance of the model and make the prediction more accurate. The establishment of random forest is based on two ideas of randomization. The specific establishment process is

shown in figure 1. The establishment process of random forest is shown as following:

1. Random selection of subtraining set: the method of resampling with bootstrap is adopted to randomly extract the same number of samples from the original data set for k times to form k data sets, and each sample set is used to construct the decision tree based on CART algorithm.

2. Random selection of sub-feature sets: like the idea of random selection of sub-training sets, each decision tree in the random forest does not make use of all features when it is established, but forms a feature data set before establishment, and randomly extracts a certain number of features from it to generate sub-training sets.

3. The decision tree construction: by the above two after randomization of the process of thought, can randomly from child training sample set and the feature set and a random sample of a building is a collection of sample a is the feature set based on the CART algorithm of decision tree, in the process of building a decision tree, don't limit the growth of the decision tree and pruning, constitute a complete growth of decision tree. Repeat the above process to generate multiple decision trees and form a random forest.

Each decision tree generates a classification result, and there is as many results as there are trees in the random forest. The final prediction result of the random forest is determined by these multiple decision trees, and the final classification result is determined by voting [10].

Fig. 1. Random forest model construction flow chart

Therefore, this paper adopts a method based on weighted k-means analysis and random forest algorithm to solve the problem of data imbalance in the

identification of suspicious transactions in bank cards. The main flow chart of this method is shown in Fig.2.

Fig. 2. Flow chart of the algorithm based on the combination of k-means algorithm and random forest algorithm

III. EXPERIMENT AND RESULTS ANALYSIS

A. The Experimental Test

The initial random forest algorithm needs to learn and model based on all data sets, and it takes a little longer to run. So 4 CPU cores are used for work. According to the above clustering results, the newly obtained tags are used as new training samples for modeling operation. The number of cluster clusters $K=7$, and the random forest model (100 trees) was used for modeling analysis.

We used the data set of suspicious bank card transactions on kaggle's data platform. The original variables included transaction amount, transaction date, transaction place, counterpart account, bank card identifier, merchant type, currency, transaction country and many others. The dataset contains 284,807 transactions, of which 492 are abnormal transactions in confirmed bank accounts, accounting for only 0.172% of the total. It is a highly unbalanced data set of positive and negative samples, and contains both categorical and continuous variables. The first step is to preprocess the data, for example, to standardize some data that is significantly different. Considering that the value range of the characteristic values of the Amount column is quite different from that of the other 28 columns processed by PCA, it is necessary to unify the standard, namely, to standardize the processing and generate new normamount, so as to eliminate the impact on the results caused by different internal compositions.

The training environment of the model adopts the built-in spyder of Anacondas. In this experiment, the original data set was randomly divided into 10 data subsets with the same number of samples and no overlap. One subset of them is taken as the test set, and the remaining 9 subsets are taken as a training set to obtain the classifier. Repeat this 10 times to obtain 10 test - training datasets. Data standardization and cross-validation were completed by scikit-learn.

B. Performance Measurement and Analysis

The suspicious transaction ratio is too small compared with the total transaction amount, which is a highly unbalanced dataset. It is clear that the commonly used classification metrics, such as accuracy and error rate, are not suitable for unbalanced problems, and a few types of data are easily treated as noise and eliminated. A well accepted measure for unbalanced dataset is AUC (area under the ROC curve). In classification problems, it is common to treat the interested classes as positive classes and other classes as negative classes. The class column in the dataset represents the sample category, 1 represents the positive class, which is the final abnormal transaction, and 0 represents the negative class, which is the normal transaction.

Almost all metrics are based on the confusion matrix, including accuracy, accuracy, recall, f1-score and, of course, AUC. The confusion matrix contains four parts of information. TP represents the actual number of samples with positive prediction, FP represents the actual number of samples with negative prediction, TN represents the actual number of samples with negative prediction, and FN represents the actual number of samples with positive prediction.

$TPR = TP / (TP + FN) = TP / \text{the number of all samples with positive truth values}$, which is the recall rate (the probability of positive classification pairs), and the ratio of the number of abnormal transactions predicted correctly to the total number of true abnormal transactions. $FPR = FP / (FP + TN) = FP / \text{the number of all the samples with negative true values}$, i.e., the false detection rate (the negative probability of misclassification), is actually the ratio of normal transactions, but the predicted number of abnormal transactions to the total number of normal transactions. The ideal model is to have TPR as high as possible and FPR as low as possible. That is to increase the recall rate while the false detection rate as low as possible.

Receiver Operating Characteristic curve: FPR on the horizontal axis and True Positive Ratio on the vertical axis. AUC: The Area Under ROC Curve. Normally, the value of AUC is between 0.5 and 1.0. The closer the value is to 1, the better the classification performance. Figure 3 is the ROC curve comparison between the suspicious transaction detection model proposed in this paper and the original stochastic forest algorithm. According to figure 3, the AUC_1 value of this model is 0.92, which is significantly higher than the AUC_2 value of the original stochastic forest algorithm, which indicates that the classification performance of this model has been effectively improved.

Fig. 3. The ROC curves obtained by the model in this paper and the random forest algorithm are compared

As can be seen from the figure 3, the ROC Curve is very close to the upper left corner, that is, the AUC (Area Under Curve) has a large area. AUC=0.92 indicates that the model has good discrimination ability. It indicates that the better the classifier's performance is, the lower the false detection rate is and the higher the recall rate is.

In terms of model evaluation, AUC, Precision, Recall, Accuracy and f1-measure are selected. As showed in table 1 below, the data are the output results of the two groups of models on the bank card data set using only random forest algorithm and weighted cluster analysis combined with random forest algorithm. By comparing the result data, it can be found that the AUC increased by 5 percentage points and f1-measure increased by 1 percentage point in the modeling results. The method proposed in this paper, which is based on the combination of k-means clustering and random forest algorithm, is an effective method to identify the

suspicious transaction detection problems of bank cards.

TABLE I. COMPARISON OF FRAUD RISK PREDICTION MODEL RESULTS

Algorithm	Accuracy	Precision	Recall	F1-measure
RF	0.86	0.90	0.91	0.91
K-means+RF	0.88	0.92	0.91	0.92

IV. CONCLUSION

This paper studies the data imbalance problem in the identification of suspicious bank card transactions based on k-means clustering and random forest algorithm. Meanwhile, AUC and Recall were used as performance evaluation criteria for unbalanced data classification. Finally, the application effect of the algorithm on the data set of suspicious bank card transactions on Kaggle data platform was tested. The experimental results show that the model in as much as possible to reduce the rate of false positives and has high ability of classification and recognition, rapid transactions data filtering timely found potential risks, to dynamically manage bank customer behavior data scientifically, improve the management efficiency of the bank, can to some extent reduce the operating cost and risk of the banking industry, to strengthen bank rapid response and improve the level of customer service has certain application value.

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